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DDES study of the WINSENT turbine blades unsteady loads under the influence of complex terrain

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Abstract. Delayed Detached-Eddy Simulation of a 750 kW wind turbine at the WINSENT complex terrain site is performed using laser-scanned blade geometry and Mann-model synthetic turbulence inflow from meteorological measurements. Simulations predict mean low-speed shaft torque of 93.34 kN m, capturing three-per-revolution loading patterns with irregular torque peaks. Flow visualization reveals that the loading variations result from blades rotating through spatially-localized low-velocity regions in the lower rotor half primarily due to the forest-terrain-affected atmospheric inflow with complex vertical velocity gradient, tower-induced velocity deficits approaching the rotor, and yawed 8.7° configuration effects. Blade-to-blade sectional load variations reach 338-679 N m⁻¹ (normal) and 128-198 N m⁻¹ (tangential) despite geometric identity, with the highest-loaded blade rotating systematically with azimuth position as blades pass through different regions within the rotor area.

1. Introduction

WINSENT (Wind Science and Engineering Test Site in Complex Terrain) is a wind energy test site situated in the mountainous terrain of southern Germany. It features two research wind turbines, each with a rated power of 750 kW, a hub height of 73 m, and a rotor diameter of 50 m [1]. High-fidelity computational fluid dynamics (CFD) studies on the wind field at this site commenced in 2016, focusing on characterizing the local flow field and evaluating the complex terrain's influence on wind speed, turbulence intensity, and boundary-layer behavior. Schulz et al. [2] carried out CFD simulations that included a generic 2.4 MW turbine with fully meshed blades, with a hub height of 95 m and a rotor diameter of 109 m virtually located at this site. The interaction of a turbine with atmospheric turbulence at this complex site was studied. Considering the same turbine, Lutz et al. [3] further examined how terrain-induced flow distortions (approximately 200 m upstream of the turbine location) affect wake development downstream to explore the complex terrain impact on the wake evolution. Building on that groundwork, Letzgus et al. [4] extended the previous CFD research to investigate turbine-flow interaction under realistic terrain-induced turbulence using fully meshed blades. Factors such as complex topography, forest canopy, and thermal stratification significantly alter the flow both at the turbine and in its wake, and that inclined or unsteady inflows can result in asymmetric rotor torque and uneven load distribution across the rotor plane.

Despite those advanced studies on characterizing upstream inflow and wake behavior, a comprehensive load analysis combining the actual measured blade with site-specific inflow data from the turbine location remains to be conducted. Recent developments are helping to supplement

previous studies on the test site. Gagnon and Lutz [5] reconstructed the geometry of the WINSENT turbine blades by transforming high-resolution laser-scanning data into a smooth CAD model, yielding accurate 2D cross-sections and a complete 3D blade surface for CFD analyses. In addition to that, 1st Intensive Observation Period (IOP-1) campaign has been conducted at the test field to gather detailed inflow and wake data. Accordingly, the present work performs Delayed Detached-Eddy-Simulation (DDES) high-fidelity CFD simulation using the real measured blade geometry and site-specific inflow conditions to evaluate the dynamic loads under real complex-terrain inflow conditions comprehensively.

Figure 1. CFD domain (solid black line) mapped onto the test site topography. The yellow star indicates the location of the northern turbine, while the white triangle marks the northwest Met Mast position. The forested region on the western (left) side of the domain coincides with a steep topographic slope featuring approximately 200 m elevation change upstream of the turbine location.

2. Methods

2.1. Atmospheric inflow characterization and generation

The inflow conditions for the simulation are derived from the IOP-1 conducted on March 31, 2025, involving coordinated measurements by the University of Tuebingen and the University of Stuttgart. The UAS measurements were used to characterize the spatial distribution of atmospheric conditions across the test site, including wind shear, turbulence intensity, thermal stratification, and wind direction consistency at multiple vertical levels. The time period 10:38-10:48 UTC was selected for simulation due to its stable mean wind direction and velocity along the measured heights, consistent turbulent intensity, and neutral thermal stratification. While the UAS measurements provided comprehensive spatial characterization, the continuous time-series velocity data (at 20 Hz sampling rate) required for synthetic turbulence generation were obtained from the northwest meteorological mast (Met Masts), which is positioned downwind of the western forested escarpment. The CFD domain (Fig. 1) was configured such that the inflow plane intersects the location of the northwest Met Mast. This configuration maintains the actual spatial distances between the measurement location and the turbine as observed in the field, and captures the forest-terrain-affected atmospheric flow recorded by the northwest Met Masts.

A turbulence length scale of $L = 27$ and anisotropy factor of $\Gamma = 2$ were found to reproduce the observed velocity spectra of the original 20 Hz Met Masts data. The data then were down-sampled by a factor of 5, yielding an effective sampling frequency of 4 Hz, and fed to Hipersim. This resulted in a Mann box with a spatial resolution of approximately 3.6 m^2 per cell, 7.56 m s^{-1} of U_{box} , and 0.19 of turbulent intensity. The synthetic turbulence inflow generation was performed using IAG's in-house turbulence generator [6], which applies the Mann spectral tensor method [7] with signal constraints to match measured U , V , and W statistics from the measurement data. The mean atmospheric boundary layer profile was established by time-averaging the measured velocities over the 10-minute period and fitting a Hellmann power-law using least-squares optimization, resulting in $z_{\text{ref}} = 57.66 \text{ m}$, and $\alpha = 0.44$. The combined mean profile and turbulence field were applied at the CFD inlet domain through the Gust boundary condition. Key atmospheric parameters characterizing the flow conditions during the selected time period are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Input signals summary of the Met Masts dataset

Anemometer	Recorded altitude [m]	Avg. incoming wind direction [°]	Avg. mean wind [m s^{-1}]	X-vel range [m s^{-1}]	Y-vel range [m s^{-1}]	Z-vel range [m s^{-1}]
Sensor 0	25.0	305.68	4.48	-1.58, 9.71	-10.4, 2.55	-4.41, 6.07
Sensor 1	46.0	303.61	7.6	0.37, 12.64	-10.19, 3.14	-3.05, 6.26
Sensor 2	72.0	301.56	8.88	1.58, 12.09	-7.83, 0.16	-1.74, 5.78
Sensor 3	97.0	302.47	8.91	3.25, 12.08	-7.63, -0.31	-1.79, 4.99

2.2. Numerical methods and solver configuration

The simulations were performed using the compressible block-structured finite-volume flow solver FLOWer, originally developed by the German Aerospace Center (DLR) [8]. The code has been extended at the Institute of Aerodynamics and Gas Dynamics (IAG) for highly resolved simulations of wind turbines in atmospheric flows. The computations were carried out on the Höchstleistungsrechenzentrum Stuttgart (HLRS). Each simulation utilized 10 compute nodes of Genoa equipped with AMD EPYC 9334 processors (64 cores per node at 2.7 GHz, 768 GB DDR5 memory). The complete 17-revolution simulation was performed approximately 300 hours of wall-clock time, using solution restart capabilities to maintain temporal continuity across job submissions. The DDES k - ω -SST turbulence model was used in the present study. A dual numerical scheme approach was adopted. The fifth-order Weighted Essentially Non-Oscillatory (WENO) scheme was applied in the background mesh region to preserve resolved turbulent structures with minimal numerical dissipation, while the more robust second-order Jameson-Schmidt-Turkel (JST) scheme was used in the near-body zones to ensure numerical stability in regions with complex geometry and steep gradients. Temporal integration was performed using dual-time stepping with a Runge-Kutta scheme, employing 100 inner iterations per physical time step. The physical time step was set to correspond to 1° of rotor azimuthal rotation, yielding $\Delta t = 0.00813 \text{ s}$ based on the operational rotational speed of 20.5 rpm during IOP-1.

2.3. Computational domain and coordinate system

The computational domain configuration is based on the measurement layout during the selected time period of IOP-1 on March 31, 2025, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The coordinate system follows a Cartesian convention with 0° pointing toward geographic east. The domain spans 512 m

Figure 2. Cut planes of the background mesh along with the turbine structures. Left image is streamwise view or X-plane, while the right image is lateral view or Y-plane (right). The cross-sectional area of **a** region on the right image is identical.

$\times 480 \text{ m} \times 516 \text{ m}$ in the streamwise (X), lateral (Y), and vertical (Z) directions, respectively. The origin (0,0) is indicated by the red dot in Fig. 1, with corresponding geographic reference coordinates (WGS84) provided for spatial context. The positive X-axis was aligned with the mean inflow direction of -212° (blue line in Fig. 1) to satisfy the constraint requirements of the synthetic turbulence generator, which assumes streamwise-aligned flow conditions. During the measurement period, the turbine nacelle was oriented at -203.3° (red line), resulting in a yaw misalignment of 8.7° between the turbine axis and the mean inflow direction. This nacelle orientation represents the actual operational state during IOP-1 and was preserved in the simulation to maintain consistency with the field measurements. The turbine was positioned 135 m downstream of the inflow boundary to perform its actual position on the test site.

2.4. Mesh generation

2.4.1. Background mesh refinement strategy

Six levels of refinement were implemented in the background mesh to ensure smooth transition from coarse to fine resolution, as shown in Fig. 2. The coarsest cells have a volume of 64 m^3 , with cell size being successively refined at a ratio of 1:2, reaching 0.015 m^3 in the immediate vicinity of the rotor blades. The grid cell cross-sectional area of the streamwise region, extending from the inflow boundary to the turbine location (Fig. 2 right), was set to 0.81 m^2 (corresponding to a linear cell spacing of 0.9 m), which is approximately one-quarter of the Mann box discretization size of 3.6 m^2 identified in Section 2.1. This refinement ratio follows established guidelines for hybrid RANS-LES simulations [9], which recommend a grid filter width satisfying $\Delta \leq L/4$, where L is the characteristic turbulence length scale and Δ represents the local grid spacing. This criterion ensures that the energetic turbulent structures are adequately resolved while maintaining computational efficiency and accuracy. The selected tunnel mesh resolution is consistent with the approach of Letzgus et al. [4], who demonstrated effective preservation of synthetic turbulence structures through the computational domain with comparable grid spacing. Further, Gagnon et al. [10] showed CFD validation with 1 m grid spacing confirmed that Gust (turbulence inflow) boundary condition accurately inserts turbulent structures at the inlet, with three velocity components (U , V , W) correlations reaching near unity and coherent structures

Figure 3. Blade surface mesh and wall-normal spacing (y^+) distribution at different viewing orientations. Top: Full blade mesh. Lower left: Spanwise view with blade at 90° (horizontal position) showing spanwise mesh refinement from root to tip. Lower right: Chordwise view with blade at 0° (vertical position) showing O-grid topology and y^+ distribution around the airfoil perimeter. The refinement distribution is intentionally adapted to local flow conditions: spanwise variation reflects increasing Reynolds number toward the tip, while chordwise variation addresses varying flow phenomena around the airfoil. The structured O-grid maintains excellent mesh quality (i-, j-, k-ratios < 1).

preserved beyond 100 m downstream.

2.4.2. Wind turbine component meshes

The turbine geometry was obtained from the reconstructed CAD models provided by Gagnon and Lutz [11]. The reference blade (serial number 022) has a tip chord length of 0.304 m and a radius of 25.02 m, as illustrated in Fig. 3. The blade pitch angle was set to 0° , corresponding to the operational settings during IOP-1. The resolution of the near-wall grid was maintained at $y^+ < 1$ throughout all solid surfaces. The blade mesh employs an O-grid topology (Fig. 3, bottom right), which provides favorable orthogonality and aspect ratio characteristics in the boundary layer region. Bangga et al. [12] demonstrated that O-grid topologies yield comparable accuracy to C-H grid configurations for wind turbine simulations while offering improved computational efficiency. The Chimera overset grid technique was employed to handle interpolation between the background mesh and the rotating turbine component grids, allowing independent mesh generation and relative motion between grid systems.

The number of cells for the complete turbine is 24.5 million cells (each blade occupies 7.06 million cells), while the complete computational mesh comprises approximately 130 million cells. All wind turbine structural surfaces (blades, hub, nacelle, and tower) were assigned no-slip wall boundary conditions with fully resolved boundary layers. The blades are modeled as rigid bodies without aeroelastic coupling in the present simulations. This assumption is appropriate for the current study's focus on atmospheric turbulence-blade aerodynamic interactions at below-rated operating conditions (7.56 m s^{-1} of U_{box}), where structural deformations are minimal and the investigated phenomena are primarily inflow-driven rather than structurally-driven. While blade flexibility would affect fatigue loads and tip deflections, these aeroelastic effects are secondary to the complex inflow-structure interaction patterns examined here. Future work will incorporate aeroelastic coupling for more complete system characterization.

3. Results

3.1. Azimuth-resolved torque analysis and flow characterization

Fig. 4 presents the instantaneous low-speed shaft (LSS) torque variation over one complete rotor revolution after 16 revolutions were simulated by which point the flow field has reached a developed state and proper temporal alignment for comparison purposes with the IOP-1 experimental data. The result shows characteristic three-per-revolution (3P) behavior. The torque oscillates between a minimum of approximately 73 kNm (at $\psi = 195^\circ$) and peaks reaching 122 kNm (at $\psi = 15^\circ$), with a mean value of 93.34 kNm. The mean CFD value shows good agreement with measured data from IOP-1, deviating by approximately 5%. The peak characteristics vary significantly across the revolution. The first peak displays smooth behavior, the second peak shows pronounced roughness with multiple oscillations, and the third peak exhibits moderate fluctuations. The deterministic 3P pattern is expected as each blade experiences systematically varying angles of attack and relative wind speeds, while rotating through the complex wind shear profile in 8.7° yawed configuration which will be discussed in the following paragraphs.

Figure 4. CFD LSS torque of the rotor, taken on the 17th revolution, compared to the IOP-1 FoWEA dataset on March 31st, 2025 at 10:43:48.33 UTC when the turbine was recorded running at 20.59 rpm. TPERIOD of the rotor to perform 1 complete revolution is 2.926829268 s.

In general, torque minima occur at three azimuthal positions: $\psi = 85^\circ$, 195° , and 315° . The minimum at $\psi = 195^\circ$ occurs in the 15° offset from the nominal tower position ($\psi = 180^\circ$) due to the 8.7° misalignment of the yaws that shifts the azimuthal interaction. This position also experiences tower-induced velocity deficit within an azimuthal range of approximately $\psi = 180^\circ \pm 30^\circ$ [13], where blades additionally operate in a retreating condition due to yaw. The retreating means that the rotational velocity opposes the incoming wind, experiencing reduced relative wind speed and consequently lower aerodynamic loading. The blade-wake interactions of the preceding blades provide minor additional contributions to load reduction, as visualized in Fig. 5a, evidenced by the positive tangential forces of Blade 1 and Blade 3 shown in Fig. 6(f) and Fig. 6(h), respectively. Flow streamline analysis on the blade surface at the torque minimum position ($\psi = 195^\circ$) confirms predominantly attached flow conditions across blade sections, with minor area of flow separation near the blade's tip. This indicating that the torque reduction is driven primarily by inflow velocity distribution rather than aerodynamic stall.

Figure 5. λ_2 -criterion visualization at $\psi = 70^\circ$ showing asymmetric blade wakes (purple) and helical tip vortices (yellow) from 8.7° yaw., (b) lateral view showing vertical velocity gradient, (c) upwind view 10 m upstream of hub center ($\psi = 70^\circ$), (d) upwind view 5 m upstream ($\psi = 70^\circ$) showing tower induction, (e) upwind view at hub center ($\psi = 15^\circ$) at torque peak with blades at 15° , 135° , 255° , and (f) upwind view at hub center ($\psi = 135^\circ$) showing similar configuration offset by 120° , torque peak. Panels c-f show translucent velocity planes, while black circles within panel c-d mark the rotor disk boundary.

Further, the reduced torque at these azimuthal positions is also caused by the spatially-localized low-velocity region in the lower rotor half introduced by the atmospheric inflow. Fig. 5b shows the lateral velocity distribution where low-velocity regions ($V_x < 2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) near the ground coincide spatially with the unsteady inflow, the Met-Masts-dataset-constrained inflow (Section 2.1) that was influenced by the forest and complex terrain on the western side of the CFD domain (Fig. 1). The atmospheric inflow structure is revealed further through velocity field visualization at different upstream locations. Fig. 5c presents the streamwise velocity distribution 10 meters upstream of the hub center, showing strong vertical velocity gradient characteristic of the atmospheric boundary layer, with the lower half exhibiting localized zones of reduced streamwise velocity due to the unsteady inflow. Fig. 5d shows the velocity distribution at 5 m upstream, where the low-velocity region in the lower half appears more evident, creating the final velocity distribution encountered by the rotor particularly within the azimuthal range $\psi = 140^\circ\text{--}220^\circ$.

On the other hand, torque peak production occurs when blade positions are not within the range of the the low-velocity regions. Fig. 5e and Fig. 5f show the rotor plane velocity distribution at $\psi = 15^\circ$ and $\psi = 135^\circ$, respectively, where torque peaks occur. Both configurations show similar blade positioning patterns with blades at azimuthal positions of 15° , 135° , and 255° (relative to the rotor azimuth reference). The third peak at $\psi = 255^\circ$ exhibits an identical blade configuration pattern, offset by 120° due to the three-bladed rotor geometry. Furthermore, the yawed configuration enhances load generation for blades within the azimuthal range $\psi = 300^\circ\text{--}90^\circ$ (spanning almost all the upper-half of the rotor when viewed from upwind) due to the advancing phenomenon, where blade rotational velocity adds vectorially to the incoming wind velocity. The variation in torque peak characteristics, smooth versus rough, reflects the blade interaction with the spatially-varying unsteady atmospheric flow field, with minor contributions from blade tip wake interactions.

3.2. Sectional Load Distribution and Blade-to-Blade Comparison

Sectional loads were extracted at 21 radial stations spanning $\frac{r}{R} = 0.07\text{--}1.0$, sampled at 1° azimuthal resolution yielding 7,560 data points per revolution for each force component. The analysis focuses on the outer blade region ($\frac{r}{R} > 0.31$), excluding the first six radial stations where structural effects dominate aerodynamic phenomena following conventions established in aerodynamic measurement campaigns [14]. Fig. 6 presents sectional load distributions comparing all three geometrically identical blades at four representative azimuth positions. Forces are reported in the blade pitch coordinate system: normal force (F_x , perpendicular to rotation) in the left column and tangential force (F_y , in plane of rotation) in the right column.

The normal force distributions (panels a, c, e, g) exhibit expected spanwise behavior, increasing from approximately 100 N m^{-1} near the blade root ($\frac{r}{R} \approx 0.31$) to peak values of $1700\text{--}2100 \text{ N m}^{-1}$ in outer regions ($\frac{r}{R} = 0.7\text{--}0.9$). However, substantial blade-to-blade variations are evident: at $\psi = 0^\circ$ (panel a), Blade 1 and Blade 3 show high normal forces (1283 and 1259 N m^{-1} , respectively) while Blade 2 exhibits significantly reduced loading (945 N m^{-1}). These variations reach $338\text{--}679 \text{ N m}^{-1}$ across different azimuth positions despite geometric identity. The tangential force distributions (panels b, d, f, h), which drive rotor torque, show expected negative values that increase in magnitude from root to tip. However, significant deviations from this expected behavior occur at specific blade-azimuth combinations, with blade-to-blade differences reaching $128\text{--}198 \text{ N m}^{-1}$ and localized regions near the blade tip showing substantially reduced or even positive values.

The most pronounced deviation occurs for Blade 2 at rotor azimuth $\psi = 0^\circ$ (panel b), corresponding to Blade 2's physical position of approximately 120° . At this position, the tangential

Figure 6. Comparison of sectional load distributions at four representative azimuth positions. Left column: Normal force (F_x , perpendicular to rotation). Right column: Tangential force (F_y , in plane of rotation). (a-b) Azimuth 0° (vertical upward); (c-d) Azimuth 90° (horizontal right); (e-f) Azimuth 180° (vertical downward); (g-h) Azimuth 270° (horizontal left). Despite geometric identity, significant instantaneous differences arise: normal force variations of 338-679 N m^{-1} and tangential force variations of 128-198 N m^{-1} . Text boxes indicate blade-to-blade differences (Δ = maximum minus minimum mean force among the three blades at each azimuth, averaged over $\frac{r}{R} > 0.31$). The systematic rotation of highest-loaded blade with azimuth demonstrates deterministic effects of wind shear and yaw misalignment.

force shows substantially reduced magnitude (mean value approximately -41 N m^{-1} across the outer blade region) compared to Blade 1 at the same rotor azimuth (-174 N m^{-1}), with positive values appearing at $\frac{r}{R} > 0.88$. This reduced or reversed tangential force indicates the blade is operating in the low-velocity region discussed in Section 3.1, experiencing reduced angle of attack and consequently lower lift generation. Similar patterns appear systematically. For example, blade 1 shows positive tangential forces at $\psi = 90^\circ$ and 180° (panels d and f), while Blade 3 exhibits this behavior at $\psi = 270^\circ$ (panel h).

The pattern of highest normal force loading rotates systematically with azimuth. Blade 3 dominates at $\psi = 90^\circ$ (1418 N m^{-1}), Blade 2 at $\psi = 180^\circ$ (1449 N m^{-1}), and Blade 1 at $\psi = 270^\circ$ (1333 N m^{-1}). This systematic rotation confirms that blades encounter different inflow conditions as they rotate through the spatially-varying atmospheric flow field. At $\psi = 0^\circ$, Blade 2's position at approximately 120° places it within the low-velocity region in the lower rotor half (Fig. 5c), explaining its reduced loading. As the rotor advances to $\psi = 90^\circ$, Blade 2 continues through the low-velocity zone while Blade 3 moves into the higher-velocity upper region and achieves peak loading. This deterministic blade-loading pattern arises from the effects of the unsteady atmospheric inflow with complex vertical velocity gradient in the lower rotor half, and 8.7° yaw misalignment, as discussed in Section 3.1.

4. Summary

This study presents a high-fidelity CFD investigation of the 750 kW WINSSENT wind turbine operating under complex terrain conditions, addressing how mountainous topography and atmospheric turbulence influence structural loads and aerodynamic performance. The analysis employs DDES with approximately 130 million grid cells using laser-scanned blade geometry and Mann-synthesized inflow from meteorological measurements during a representative 10-minute period. The simulation operated at 20.5 RPM with 0° blade pitch and 8.7° yaw misalignment, employing rigid blade modeling appropriate for the below-rated conditions examined.

CFD predictions yield mean LSS torque of 93.34 kN m with three-per-revolution loading periodicity characterized by irregular torque peaks. Flow field visualization reveals that the loading variations within one revolution are primarily driven by spatially-localized low-velocity regions in the lower rotor half, due to the forest-terrain-affected atmospheric inflow (with complex vertical velocity gradient), tower-induced velocity deficits approaching the rotor, and yaw effects. In addition, flow streamline analysis confirming predominantly attached flow conditions, indicating that torque and load variations are driven primarily by inflow velocity distribution rather than aerodynamic stall. Sectional load analysis demonstrates that despite geometric identity, blades exhibit substantial load variations of $338\text{-}679 \text{ N m}^{-1}$ (normal) and $128\text{-}198 \text{ N m}^{-1}$ (tangential), with the highest-loaded blade rotating systematically with azimuth position as blades pass through different regions within the rotor area. The analysis reveals unusual load distributions (positive tangential forces and reduced normal forces) when blades operate in low-velocity zones.

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